

Literature of Pandemic: An Analytical Study of Select Literary Texts

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Abstract

Change is a natural phenomenon. Everything we come across changes with time. This change occurs through evolution, a continuous and ever-changing process. Humans' present form is also the result of evolution. The history of evolution proceeds through various unwanted incidents. One such is the Pandemic that occurs age after age belittling humans and their progress. It brings death, destruction, and enormous devastation for a certain period. Later, humans revive it and come back to their usual selves. Though humans use to forget the impact of epidemics with the flying of time, literary history bears it through its creative artistic works. From ancient times to the present, literature chronicles every incident. The present paper aims to depict the relationship between literary works and the Pandemic. It also attempts to explore various socio-economic facts that people had to undergo during the time of the pandemic. It may also try to present the nature of literary works, and how these texts express the problems of plague victim people, which resulted in physiological and psychological puzzles.

Keywords: destruction, evolution, literature, pandemic, phenomenon

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1. Introduction

The history of humanity chronicles many deadly diseases that have occurred in different ages since the creation of the earth. Sometimes it was caused by external natural phenomena, sometimes by any fatal disease, creating havoc and damage to the whole world. People are powerless victims in front of those diseases. They are mere toys in such conditions. Not all the time, people accept it easily; they try to fight against it with the help of science and medicine. Despite that, they have to bear extensive losses due to spreading diseases, making humans face the disruption of social, economic, and political equilibrium. After the Pandemic stage is over, people get relief from it. Still, it results in traumatic, psychological, and physical disorders. Generation after generation has to bear the adversative sides of the Pandemic.

One such Pandemic occurred during the twenty-first century named, Covid-19. After the Second World War, this Pandemic created a never-ending mark in the history of human civilization. It not only occurs in one country but has a worldwide impact. It disables the balance of nature and human society. China was the first country affected by the disease, and very soon, it spread worldwide. Its fast advances made people afraid. When a large number of people started to die all over the world, the WHO declared it an epidemic. Most countries followed the lockdown to protect their land from the hands of those who had come from affected countries. Bus, trains, cars, and even plains were also canceled. Every country closed down its markets, shops, schools, colleges, factories, and other working places so that no one came close to others and got affected by others. It is a disease that spreads through the air from one man to another. Within a few months, one human became the enemy of another human. Everyone feared that they could be affected by others who came close to him.

People used to wear masks whenever they needed to go outside and washed their hands when they returned to their homes. They started to follow social distancing. News channels are always used to highlight what steps should be taken to avoid the infection of the disease. People became jobless and spent their time in their houses morosely. The education system was the worse sufferer. Due to the lockdown, schools and colleges were closed. Students forgot their study time because they feared that anything could happen anytime. They lose their average energy in reading. Even in the family, everybody looked at themselves with suspicious eyes. It is as if they are their enemy living under one shed.

This disease caused uncountable deaths leading to a dramatic loss of human lives worldwide. Does it pose the existential question-who is the human? Are they mere puppets in the hands of fate? Living is a blessing to everyone during the Pandemic, as the number of deaths crosses one lakh per day. The majority of people lack social protection and need quality health care. During this Pandemic, no productivity was there. Due to the loss of jobs, people faced a financial crisis and could not feed themselves and their families. Millions of agricultural workers regularly faced high poverty levels due to this disease. And those who had been working outside their homeland could not be able to return to their homeland. The most tragic incident arrived when they died, and their dead bodies were buried without a proper burial.

Before Covid-19, European people faced Black Death, the second to strike Europe during the late middle ages. The first one is the Great Famine of 1315-1317. It affected Europe violently, causing the death of many people. The famine emerged with the bad weather in 1315. Farmers failed to produce crops until 1317. Alongside the crop failure, cattle disease caused the sheep and cattle to fall as much as 80%. The price of food began to be rising, and it became almost double. This brought great famine. People thought it was divine retribution. It also undermined the institutional authority of the church. The famine begot class warfare and political strife, disestablishing the entire region. They stole everything from others to feed their children and family members. The condition went so worse that people began to eat dogs and horses. Even the law-abiding people were restored to criminality only to continue their daily lives.

After the Great Famine, the Black Death created a black chapter in human history. It killed almost 75 to 200 million people. The infection is caused chiefly by the bacterium *Yersinia*. It affected the countries like North Africa, Austria, Hungary, Switzerland, Germany, and others. It was believed that a ship from Calais carried the plague to Dorset. It resulted in a drastic change due to the catastrophic death of the people. The lands became complete with dead bodies. This also caused the ruin of many landowners. The city population was diminished drastically. It caused the disappearance of almost a thousand villages in England. This enormous biological crisis led to sociocultural changes such as a shortage of labor, the end of serfdom, and the creation of a free peasantry. The global flu or influenza pandemic of 1918-1919 overlapped with

World War I. It was estimated that almost one-third of the population is affected by this disease. Around 50 million people died all over the country.

It's a fact that the pandemic occurs deliberately in history. Whenever it appears, it destroys a social structure, economic stability, and the psychological strength of the people. A pandemic is a phenomenon which makes humans aware of what to do and how to behave in front of any deadly disease. It on the one hand unites people and on the other develops the fighting spirit of the people. Helpless people acquire the ability to face the pandemic heroically. So, the pandemic is important. Sometimes pandemic is used to destroy a whole society to give it a new birth. This study shows how pandemics were used deliberately to bring out the good in humans. Through the analysis of various texts, it aims to point out the hidden qualities of people that are expressed in problematic situations. Its target is to present the nature of diseases and how these diseases help people to come out of them. The objective of the study is to depict the texts from the thirteenth century to the present to show how humanity has been deliberately facing pandemics age after age.

2. Definition of Pandemic Literature

A pandemic is something that deals with death, destruction and decay. It is the dark side of human history. Whenever a pandemic appeared, it created a huge impact on all things. Literature is one such that is intricately related to the pandemic. Literature, through its literary creations, tries to present the pandemic in its own form. Therefore, pandemic literature is that literature which deals with the effects of the pandemic on the arts. The relationship between the pandemic and literature is intertwined. Literature chronicles the pandemic age after age. Pandemic literature arouses the eyes of the readers as it helps them to know the socio-political condition of the pandemic time. Scientific diaries and history also provide an account of the pandemic, but literature is different from that as it can grapple with the pity and fear of the readers through the presentations of the ups and downs of the characters' lives. Through its presentation of the emotion of the characters, it attracts the attention of the readers.

3. Review of Pandemic Literature

If anyone investigates the literary works of writers of several ages, s/he can easily understand what types of epidemics appeared in human history. Literature states pandemics and epidemics through the production of various texts by multitalented writers who tried to present the outbreak and its impact on people of all classes. In the Bible, the plague is considered something that the Gods provide in the form of punishment. It may be viewed as a warning against the movement of Israelites instructing them to behave morally. This causal relationship between pandemic and sin is also found in Greek literary texts such as Homer's *Iliad* and Sophocles' *Oedipus the King*. *Iliad* depicts the plague as divine punishment, which attacked not only men but also dogs and mules. There were uncountable deaths of men and animals. In *Oedipus the King*, the plague is a miasma rather than just a disease that brought huge destruction.

This mainly happened, as they believed because they allowed a cursed person to harbor there. The plague destroyed crops, animals, and babies. Besides, the Greek historian Thucydides and Latin post-Lucretius described the supernatural origin of the diseases focusing on the description of uncontrollable fear among the citizens. They believed that the plagues caused selfishness and avarice among people, and it did inflict on all irrespective of good and evil. Boccaccio in *Decameron* and Geoffrey Chaucer in *The Canterbury Tales* captured the effect of the plague that occurred in the Middle Age. They focused on the rise of greed, avarice, vice, and corruption among people and pointed to the degeneration of human behavior at that time. *Journal of the Plague Year* by Daniel Defoe gave a detailed narration of events, anecdotes and statistics regarding the 1665 Great Plague. Italian novelist Alessandro Manzoni pointed out the detailed description of the plague that hit Milan almost around 1630 in his two works *The Betrothed* and *History of the Column of Infamy*. English gothic writer Mary Shelley in her *The Last Man* described a future world ravaged by plague. The novel also depicted how people use to avoid each other during the time of the plague, mostly those people who considered themselves immune to the disease. Edgar Allan Poe in his short story "The Masque of Red Death" presented plague by focusing on the metaphorical element of death. Here the author meditated on the inevitability of death and how people were plagued by death. With the advent of the nineteenth century, the definition of plague started to change. People are not in a position to accept the plague as a divine phenomenon. Scientists describe that plagues are mainly caused by various

bacteria and germs that infect humans. People start to take the plague as a natural phenomenon. Jack London in *The Scarlet Death* not only gives the details of the plague but also presents humans' acceptance of the plague caused by bacteria. He also presents how the dead bodies decompose very rapidly releasing billion of germs. Marissa Meyer in *Cinder* describes the Blue Fever or the Letumosis disease that causes havoc on the people and quarantines a whole race. Carole Stivers in *The Mother Code* describes a future city which faces the death of human beings due to an unknown disease. The disease kills newborn babies and their mothers. It leads scientists to take the help of artificial mothers to bring up immune children placing them far away from the city.

4. Analysis of Select Pandemic Texts

Boccaccio described a detailed picture of the contemporary society of his time through his artistic work *Decameron*. His depiction of the terrible suffering scenes of people and their interpersonal betrayal affect the readers highly. The people affected by the Black Death were terrified when they saw the black marks growing on their bodies. They knew that this was the apparent symptom of death. Anyone affected by this could not survive. Their immediate death imagination made their minds unstable and agitated. As per Boccaccio, almost 10000 people died within the walls of Florence. He narrates the physical, social and psychological sufferings of the people on the streets with plague boils and buboes. Due to this plague, the social order was ruined. Most of the people withdrew to protect themselves. Robbers deliberately stole money and valuable things from the houses of the neighbouring people. The feudal order was out of work, ill and weak. People started to lose their faith in religion and God. The whole society was imbalanced.

Alongside feudalism and belief, the church system was destroyed. The world had become upside down. The church failed to deliver its religious message to the people. Its virtuosity was getting dimmed regularly. The church officials also engaged themselves in sinful activities. The holy men tried to seduce the girls of the town. One of the sacred men locked a girl in his cell and put the key to the abbot as he had noticed the abbot was coming towards him. When the holy man realized he could be caught red-handed, he fictionalized a false story and thus saved himself from being revealed. In this way, he ridiculed the rule-bound nature of the church's ideas of sin.

Though he was successful in keeping himself safe from the hands of the abbot, he broke the trust of the people and the church. He would not be taken as an example of virtue. Instead, he would be the epitome of depravity to whom bodily pleasure was more important than spiritual and humanistic value. Boccaccio's point of view was that plague ruined the usual mental set of all types of people. That's why they engaged in sinful acts without thinking about the outcome of it. The epidemic had demoralized their mental setup. They forgot their duty toward society and towards their profession. Though it may be the stupidity of the people not to understand the future impact of their activities, they did it only to benefit the ruined society. To them, the present helpful value of bodily pleasure was more important than the outstanding futuristic respectable works. They wanted to enjoy the present moment as there was no surety of the unpredictable future in this plague.

Boccaccio's depiction of the plague offers a realistic account of the epidemic, its symptoms, and its impact on the country's people. Through this work provides the tragic story of the plague as well as he sets the play as an example of jealousy, hatred, lust, anger, and virtue. Decameron can also be taken as an instance to the readers of how to overcome the plague and how love and purity dominate over any disease. It opens up a new way for the twenty-first-century citizen to come out of depression, disease, and mental trauma. It teaches modern people that the corona situation and social distancing are not new phenomena; it has continued since immemorial. Florentine people had armed themselves against the ongoing plague. They followed moderation and serenity to avoid the current situation. Even read many positive stories to overcome the epidemic and contain mental peace before the massive outbreak. So, Decameron can be taken as a remedy to face Covid-19 as it is based on the experience of people who, like Covid affected country persons, met a deadly plague once.

Journal of the Plague Year by Daniel Defoe is the second one that provides us with a clear picture of the great plague that devastated Europe in the eighteenth century. Defoe wrote the book as a warning informing the country people that plague in Marseilles could cross into England anytime. He advised people what to do to avoid the curse. It also describes the condition of London streets, alleys, churchyards, and pubs. People initially did not know they were affected by it, so they carried it unknowingly. Due to this plague, twenty percent of the people had to face death. The outbreak was believed to have started in December 1664 after the goods were

imported from Holland. Initially, the number of fatalities was few and restricted to St. Giles and Long Acre. By June, there was a sign of change as the disease spread throughout the whole city. Low-level fear and uneasiness began to grow among the city people. What kind of pathetic situation did city people face when a mother killed her children in her lunacy? The case not only creates fear but also gathers the readers' sympathy. His depiction of the people who regularly died on the street brings the reader's sympathy towards them, who have nothing to do but accept death openly. The dead bodies were laid on the road in such a way that they were of no value and were there just to be cremated by the government. The rest of the people who were alive used to avoid the highways full of dead bodies. There was no sympathy for fellow human beings. Earlier, people used to arrange a proper burial for dead bodies. Now the situation is different. People used to get scared of dead bodies as the dead bodies might infect the living ones. This work is a testimony to the grim reality of life. Fear of death has changed all the good of human beings. It is also true that everyone will try to save themselves and their near and dear ones when there is death in a life situation. It is the existential crisis of the whole city.

Years of Wonder: A Novel of the Plague by Geraldine Brooks is also centered on the theme of the Pandemic. It is based on the true stories of the village, Eyam. It was under the threat of a Pandemic spread in London and is carried on to the town through the character George. After him, most of the villages got affected by the disease. But the villagers made an excellent decision to save the entire city. They quarantined themselves and did not allow anyone to cross the village border. They sacrificed not for themselves but for the good of humanity. It may be that they could be cured of the disease if taken to the city hospital, but there also lies the risk that the city people might get affected by them. Their decision placed them as logically minded citizens of the globalized world. Through their self-sacrifice, they put themselves in the position of martyrs who sacrifice for the country's greater good. Besides, Anna's role in helping Michael Mompellion and his high-born wife set the example of good-natured human beings even in a state of dire crisis. Brooks presents two themes equally- weaving a highly readable tale of immense pain, degradation, and fear and of ultimate truth.

Mary Shelley's *The Last Man* is an apocalyptic novel, dealing with the issue of the Pandemic. To Mary Shelley, the disease was a common factor that shattered her mentally, physically, and psychologically. She lost her mother due to puerperal fever. Her son William died

at three after being attacked by malaria. Her daughter Clara died because of dysentery at age one. Even her husband, Percy Shelley, committed suicide. Deaths and diseases made her life unbearable. This led her to write the novel *The Last Man*, which speaks about the worldwide Pandemic of that time. The book is set in the twenty-first century. Lionel Verney narrates it. His friend was Benevolent Lord Protector. Verney, his friend, his sisters, and their lovers were engaged in an intricate relationship with each other, which made the government busy solving their problems. As a result, state officials failed to take immediate steps for the Pandemic. It led to a series of natural disasters that intensified the plague. Among the incidents are the black sun, tidal surges, earthquakes, etc. Several poets died because of this disease. It recounts the history of massive losses that Europe had to bear. People felt isolated and traumatized, which is reflected through the actions of the novel's characters. The book ends with the destruction of the human race.

Close to the side of the story of deaths, the novel also portrays the story of the extinction of human civilization, which collapsed due to the outbreak of the unstoppable plague. The human population started to become extinct daily. But Shelley argues that the Pandemic not only brings the destruction of the human race but also it helped nature to be nourished. The more people died, the more survivors emerged, making the biodiversity balanced. The world began to regain the natural beauty that was lost before the plague due to the development of Industrialization. Her novel presents a human-less world that is in the process of regaining its vitality. This work presents a world that was reviving its lost spirit and strengths.

Cholera that spread from 1817 to 1824 throughout the Indian subcontinent terrified humanity. The economic stability of the people was damaged after this deadly Pandemic. The prosperity of the nation is at stake at that time. The whole country had to encounter extensive loss. Despite its adverse side, it united the people irrespective of class, gender, and race. Their motto was to fight against the disease jointly. Survival was more important to them. Art, politics, and faith failed to define humanity; humanity is defined by fellow feeling, compassion, and community. The novel also makes it clear that humans are not the sole authority in the universe; humans are one of the species among others. If they need to survive, they must depend on other beings. This is the Post-anthropocentric view, which states that all beings on earth have equal rights. This stands in contrast to anthropocentrism, which argues that humans are the universe's

controlling factor. Humans are the most valuable and rational beings on earth; they must be protected at any cost. Due to this, humans dominate the whole world and try to control the lives of others on earth.

Albert Camus' *The Plague* is a documentary of the plague that destroyed the city of Oran. It was published in 1947. It is told from the point of view of a narrator. It presents a snapshot of life in Oran as seen through the author's distinctive absurdist point of view. This is the fictional account of the plague that Camus tries to present here. He offers people's experiences during the epidemic; it isn't easy to survive in such situations. First, in the city of Oran, rats started to die. People got afraid of sudden unnatural deaths. This fear transformed into a panic when one of the city people died from a strange fever. When the number of deaths increased, the government closed the city gates and quarantined the city, of Oran. People of that city believed that it was a divine punishment. Considering it, they started to leave the city. The problem occurs when in other places, they were treated as criminals. Tarrou, one of the characters, organized an anti-plague sanitation league, and many volunteers joined to help. The death toll is so high that authorities have to cremate the bodies. Characters watched each other die in front of them. They performed the role of the observer. Then the people started to fight back, though they knew very well that the victory was temporary over the plague as the bacteria would lie dormant in that city.

Camus' primary purpose is to show that the world is meaningless and absurd. There is no God or cosmic order. Humans are doomed to suffer and die. The town he presents is the microcosm of the whole universe. The book is more than a tale about the disease; it is also an intensely layered meditation on the human condition and the obligations humans have to undergo. It stresses the powerlessness of the individual characters to affect their destiny. It is an atheist world with no reason to blame fate or others. Camus uses the epidemic to explore relationships, community, and existence. It also may be taken as men's propensity towards chaos and evil while ultimately remaining good. The text uses plague to refer to how humans choose life. Do the people of Oran will accept the epidemic without any true thinking or accept death as a complex way of life and receive it as the gift of divinity? It lies in the hands of the humans whether they should face death bravely or flee from the fearful thought of death and accept life as it is. In this way, the book throws several questions relating to the nature of destiny and human conditions.

The Scarlet Plague by Jack London centres on the Red Death epidemic. The novel deals with the 2073 futuristic world in which the narrator recounts the events that happened sixty years before the novel's actual setting. The book is narrated by James Smith, one of the survivors of the Red Death disease. He was an English professor. The disease came out when he was young. Due to the rapid spreading of the disease, people felt scared of the disease. The victims' faces started to be scarlet, and they felt numbness in the lower portion of their bodies. Affected people died within 30 minutes of the disease. There was no cure at that time. The doctors failed to provide treatment to the patients. One day, while James was teaching, one of his students became senseless and died within a few minutes. The whole campus was sealed. When James came to his house, his family members accepted him with suspicion on him as they believed that he was also affected by that disease. Later, the whole area was affected by the disease. Only a few were there after the period of the disease was over. *The Scarlet Plague* provides a fictionalized account of the Pandemic Red Death that killed the lives of billions of people. It is similar to Covid 19 as both diseases decimated the human population and made human civilization suffer with bare survival. The novel also sets in 2013, six years earlier than Covid. The Red Death disrupted the usual way of people's lives, making them face socio-economic challenges. People at the beginning took the disease lightly, believing that the doctors would undoubtedly find out a way of the disease. But later, it resulted in a life-threatening one.

Like *The Scarlet Plague*, Marissa Meyer's *Cinder* is also a futuristic novel set in New Beijing. The title character is Cinder, who is a cyborg. She is a mechanic by profession. She has her companion Iko who is an android. She lives with her stepmother and two sisters. Their city is under the threat of Letumosis disease. Their neighbor Chang Sacha is the first one attacked by the disease. Later, Cinder's sister Peony also gets the disease. Their mother, Adri, thinks it is because of Cinder, Peony is ill as the infection spreads from the market, and Cinder works in the market as a mechanic. When the government accepts humans, androids, and cyborgs for the trial of the disease, Adri donates Cinder for the trial of the anti-dote, though Cinder does not do so as it may lead her to die untimely. But later, it is revealed that Cinder has the antibody immune. She has developed a healthy relationship with Dr. Erland during the trial process. Even Prince Kai, would be king of the city, like Cinder. Kai's father also died because of the disease. The

government quarantines the citizens who are affected by the disease. Their family members are also quarantined if they bear the light symptoms of the disease.

Cinder opens up a scope to critically discuss the characters that attacked and their attitude towards each other. Cinder's mother, Adri, is presented here as a foil to Cinder. However, Cinder's mother does not have any sympathy toward Cinder. When she knows that in the market, one of their neighbors is the victim of Letumosis, she does not allow Cinder to stay in her house. She does not have minimum love for Cinder; otherwise, she cannot send her for the trial of the disease. It may be that in the trial process, Cinder can die. She does not even ask Cinder whether she agrees with the fact or not. It is as if Cinder is her possession. Cinder has no opinion of her own; she has to obey her mother's orders. While the government officials have come to take Cinder away, she cries and requests her mother not to send her there. The disease may kill her. But Adri was too adamant to care for her earnest appeal. To Adri, money is more important than her daughter. She only wants the money the government will provide her family for sending her children for the trial. This is how the novel presents a different story of the mother-daughter relationship. The relationship between the mother and her daughter is upside down. It may also be that due to her Cinder identity, she is neglected by her mother.

Apart from Adri, her other sister Pearl always wants to get rid of Cinder. Like Adri, she also despises her vehemently. When Cinder returns to her house from the market, Pearl opposes Cinder. She supports her mother in not allowing Cinder in the house. Even when Cinder wants to join the ball, Pearl insults her, saying that a machine will dance! Peony, Cinder's other sister, is opposite Adri and Pearl. She always supports Cinder. She loves Cinder very much. While all her family members chide Cinder, she stands beside Cinder. Though Peony is identified as a victim of Letumosis, she does not believe that Cinder is the cause of her disease. She tells Cinder that she must not feel guilty for her disease. Cinder also returns her favor and love. When Cinder knows she has the antibody cell within her, she immediately goes to meet Peony, avoiding the risks of her life. There she informs her that the vaccine will come soon and she will not have to worry much. She has to be mentally strong and fit, as it will help her to fight against the disease. Even she requested Dr. Erland to give Peony the first dose of the vaccine. When the vaccine is prepared, she steals a vaccine for Peony and saves her life. This is how Peony and Cinder present

here an affectionate sisterly relationship. Amid betrayal, rejection, and avoidance, these two sisters represent love and trust in each other.

Cinder is also a story of an updated modern society where humans live and accept the citizenship of androids, medoids, and cyborgs. These artificial beings are also engaged in different fields of activities. Some androids work as newspaper reporters. Medroids are busy sending people into quarantine, and thus they save the lives of many people. If humans do the same work, they can also be affected by the disease. But Medroids cannot receive the disease because they are not humans but rather machines. They will not have to face death, unlike humans. People will not also be affected by them. Apart from that, androids and cyborgs are used for the trial process, which may indirectly reduce the deaths of people. If humans are used instead of artificial beings, they have to bear the adverse effect of the disease; it may be that the disease can infect them. Therefore, technology helps to save human lives.

5. Conclusion

To conclude, it can be said that the Pandemic is a natural and normal phenomenon that has been happening since the birth of humans. It brings death and destruction to humans and the world. For a certain period, it continues to reign over humans. But after that initial period, every human started to fight against it. The more the day passes, it uses to lose its magnanimity. Apart from its opposing sides, it has its positive aspects. It reduces traffic accidents as no vehicles are on the road during the Pandemic. Nature gets time to recover itself. Many unknown animals have started to flourish in the natural world. Aquatic biodiversity improves as all the factories are locked due to the absence of men at that time, and there is no water pollution. The Pandemic helps to build genuine relationships with family members as all are quarantined at home. It also gives birth to a new wave of tools and systems like online e-service, home delivery, etc. The education system is also digitalized, which helps students to continue their study digitally. Staying at home gives the benefit of developing better hygiene as almost everyone may try to follow yoga and free-hand practices to make them fit mentally and physically.

Boccaccio's *Decameron* provides a brief account of love and trust among people despite the deadly conditions faced by people. It is the work that helps to build a positive mental set-up in a state of dire crisis. Geraldine Brooks' *Years of Wonder* is also a tale of logical-minded citizens who died through suffering and still not allowed the disease to spread all over the city so that the other citizens may be safe from the disease. Mary Shelley's *The Last Man* points out the posthumanism angle stating that every species on earth has the equal right to survive. It is a world of cohabitation and coexistence of all beings irrespective of humans, animals or other beings. Camus' *The Plague* questions the purpose of human existence. It depicts the helplessness of people in the hands of destiny and the destruction of the belief of humans in Gods and divine figures. *The Scarlet Plague* by London presents separate views of the family members. One member of a family appears strange to others if s/he has become the victim of a deadly disease. It is a novel about the internal division of family life. Whereas Meyer's *Cinder* brings up a new way of looking at the disease and its cure, as it is the novel that depicts the uses of artificial beings for the trial process of diseases. Earlier humans did not have the idea that cyborg figures can be taken for the production of vaccines. This novel makes clear the positive aspects of machines and artificial beings.

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6. References

- Boccaccio, G. (1995). *The Decameron*. Penguin Books.
- Brooks, G. (2001). *Years of Wonder: A Novel of the Plague*. Viking Press UK.
- Camus, A. (1991). *The Plague*. New York: Vintage Books.
- Defoe, D. (2003). *A Journal of the Plague Year: Being Observations or Memorials, Of the most Remarkable Occurrences, As well Publick as Private which Happened in London During the Last Great Visitation in 1665*. Penguin Classics.
- London, J. (1912). *The Scarlet Plague*. Macmillan.
- Meyer, M. (2012). *Cinder*. Feiwel & Friends: Macmillan.
- Pokhrel, S., & Chhetri, R. (2021). *A Literature Review on Impact of Covid-19 Pandemic on Teaching and Learning*. Higher Education for the Future. DOI: 10.1177/2347631120983481.
- Shelley, M. (1826). *The Last Man: The Author of Frankenstein*. Henry Colburn.